

DESTINY AS A LINGUOCULTURAL CONCEPT**Abdurakhimova F.K.****Sherbutayeva R.**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098409>

Astract. The article is devoted to topical issues of conceptualization and formation of ideas about the world and the place of man in it. The authors aim to identify diachronic and synchronic characteristics of the concept of fate, typical for several linguistic and cultural communities. The scientific novelty of the article lies in the study of precedent phenomena as an effective way to reveal the content of the concept in language and culture. The main result of the work is the conclusion that precedent statements and situations serve as key representatives of the concept of fate in language and culture.

Keywords: concept, conceptualization, precedent phenomenon, fate, perception invariant, meaning

Any concept, including the concept of fate, has a complex semiotic representation: in natural language, rituals and beliefs, graphic art, etc. It should also be noted that each concept has a long history: it is in a state of continuous development, design and re-registration. In the broadest sense of the word, a concept is a set of all symbolic embodiments of the results of cognition of phenomena that are not given to a person in direct sensory experience. In a narrow sense, a concept is everything that we think and express in natural language about a particular phenomenon that is significant for the individual's consciousness, national consciousness, and culture . Our thoughts, or in other words, our interpretations of what we have seen, heard, and experienced, form the basis of a picture of the world that includes the person himself. At the same time, as N. N. Boldyrev rightly notes, "a person does not reflect the world, its objects, events and relationships between them as they are. He constructs the surrounding world in his consciousness, establishing, among other things, different types of logical relations between objects and events" [Boldyrev 2015: 5].

The significance of the concept is based on its historical continuity or tradition traced in different cultural languages (verbal art, painting, music, etc.); its influence on the standards of behavior, and its leading role in the formation of socio-cultural patterns.

The concept could be represented in the form of a dynamic semiotic model, in which different stages of formation are distinguished, subsystems with stable and sudden intersections, shifts in time layers, etc. Elena Samoilovna

Kubryakova pointed out that the semantic structure of a word changes gradually, while "the conceptual structure of some keywords undergoes radical transformations" [Kubryakova 1991: 85]. At the same time, the intensity of a word can remain relatively stable, and its extension can get a new development, and, "connecting new experience with old", it can move into new paradigms of knowledge [ibid.]. Thus, the separation of semantic and conceptual analysis is not questioned: "semantic analysis is related to the explanation of the word that leads to knowledge about the world" [ibid.]. Much later, this idea was developed by L. A. Gruzberg. She noted the active use of component analysis by researchers of concepts and drew attention to the difference in the tasks solved using this analysis. According to the scientist, in the framework of the cognitive approach, not semes are extracted from the content of the concept, but meanings, "the totality of which is the internal content of the concept" [ibid.]. Earlier, E. V. Ilchuk wrote about the connection between meaning and a language sign: "In speech, the meaning ... assigned to a language sign makes up the information that the sign conveys about its denotation" [Ilchuk 2005: 26]. L. A. Gruzberg also outlined a way to extract meanings – the study of the concept in precedent texts. The authors of this article expand the boundaries of such an approach and believe that the meanings that constitute a linguoculturological concept should be sought in the whole variety of precedent phenomena-from a precedent name to a precedent situation. The precedent phenomenon (PF) included in speech reflects an individual's knowledge of the world and how a language symbol is identified with certain qualities. Precedent phenomena can perform the identification signal function of "friend or foe" and, because of this, there cannot be a single, averaged and unchangeable version of the perception of certain situations, texts or personalities within a single language community. In other words, a precedent phenomenon as a fact of linguistic culture and experience can relate to different perceptions. The invariant perception of PF is possible only in certain linguistic and cultural groups united by similar language and life experience, a close worldview and a common rating scale. From this it follows that the invariant of perception of PF acts as a kind of beginning that connects intra-group ideas and stereotypes.

The key concept of FATE for many communities and cultures continues to attract the attention of researchers [The concept of fate 1994; Eidinow 2011; Gryshchenko 2016]. This state of affairs is not surprising, since a person's life proceeds in constant interaction with the surrounding world and society. As a result of this interaction, an existential space is created, i.e. "the space of a

person's true existence, ... the reference point in which is the innermost "I" as the value core of the individual". The human mind persistently comprehends everything that "relates to the person himself, to society, to nature" (Conrad 1972, p. 473). Understanding one's own "I", its original role in the course of life, inevitably began with the question of whether a person is able to determine the course of his own life. Thinkers of different eras tried to understand whether it is possible to influence it, direct its movement, or whether it is predetermined in advance and neither the mind nor the will of a person can change anything.

In the above-quoted work "On the Meaning of History", which has become a classic, Nikolai Iosifovich Konrad wrote that humanity has developed two most typical answers to this question. The first is the conviction that "the life of a person, society and the whole world goes on independently of the will and desires of a person"; the second is the statement that "the life of a person and society is created by people themselves".

The recognition of the first answer resulted in an unquestioning belief that there is some kind of force controlling the existence of people.

This belief, as a kind of cognitive basis of ideas about fate, is implicitly expressed in a precedent statement from Virgil's poem "Aeneid": *dare fatis vela* "to trust to fate" (literally: "to entrust the sails to fate") [Vergilius]. The leading conceptual features of the representation of ideas about fate in ancient Anglo-Saxon texts were the omnipotence of fate, its ignorance and mystery, which is confirmed by the formula (precedent) phrases *Wyrd ne cuþon* [Beowulf] "fate did not know", *wyrd ne ful cuþe* [Juliana] "fate did not know at all".

The idea underlying the first of the above-mentioned types of view of fate is evident in the Greek word *μοίρα* "moira". Its literal meaning "part, share" served as the basis for the metaphorical transfer of the substantive to the designation of the abstract concept of "fate" – the scenario of life that is given to a person at birth. We can talk about the clarity of the semantic transition and the accuracy of the secondary meaning. However, it is rather difficult to describe the meaning that emerged as a result of the secondary nomination, which is somewhat confirmed by the Mythological Dictionary edited by E. M. Meletinsky, which states that Moira does not have a "distinct anthropomorphic appearance", and her image is "rare in ancient art" [Mythological Dictionary 1991: 374].

Ideas about the three women who determine the fate of a person at birth can be found in the beliefs and rituals of the southern and eastern Slavs, about which S. M. Tolstaya wrote in some detail. So, it was believed that on the third day after the birth of a child, three angels came to the house at midnight: the eldest

predicted death, the middle-diseases and injuries, the youngest announced the time when a person would marry or get married and, in fact, determined everything that would happen to him in life [Tolstaya 2008: 349].

The number three turns out to be significant in the general context of ideas about fate. You can recall, for example, the three cards that were supposed to determine the fate of Herman in *The Queen of Spades* by A. S. Pushkin.

In the initial ideas of Moira-fate is embodied in a certain material object-a fetish. In Greek mythology, the fate of Meleager, the winner of the javelin and javelin throw in all-Greek games, was enclosed in an unburned log, which his mother, Alpheia, snatched from the fire, extinguished and hid. When Meleager killed his mother's brother, Alpheia, obsessed with revenge, decided to destroy her son – she threw a once-hidden brand into the fire and Meleager died a martyr's death [Mythological Dictionary 1991].

Material or fetish motivation underlies the semantics of modern English the word lot "fate, fate" goes back to the Old English word hlot "part, share of something". Later, in the Middle English period, the substantive lothlot lot<hlotdeveloped the meaning of "a thing; a piece of something that gets as a result of choice, competition" from which then, as a result of metaphorical transfer, the meaning "fate" is formed.

The Russian word "lot", according to V. I. Dahl, meant "a piece, a cut, a segment, a particle, a particle of crumbled, chopped". And also "a segment with a mark for throwing and deciding fate, happiness of something controversial" (hence "throwing lots) [Dahl 1995: 534].

Many lexical units that relate to the idea of fate in different linguistic and cultural communities have the same semantic motivations. The meaning of becoming, movement, and rotation is found in the linguistic means of representing the concept of fate in Ancient Germanic languages. The Old Norse *Ur- r*, Old English *Wyrd*, and Old High German *Wurt* are derived from the Indo-European root *uer-t "to rotate, to twist" (Pokorny 1959).

The idea of fate as a spinning wheel entered European culture in the Middle Ages thanks to the precedent text *Consolation of the Philosophy* of Boethius, although such an understanding of fate existed long before the appearance of this work of the Roman philosopher. This idea is a key one in many of Shakespeare's works. Так, в «Короле Лире» шут говорит: Let go thy hold when a great wheel runs down a hill, lest it break thy neck with following; but the great one that goes upward, let him draw thee after (Shakespeare. *King Lear*) " ogo to the side when the big wheel rolls down the mountain, so that it does not break you neck, but

grab it when it goes up the mountain "(here and further translated by B. Pasternak).

The meaning of weaving is the oldest in the ideas of fate. Moira Clotho spins the thread of fate. TheuebhLatin word fatom (English fortune) and the Old English substantive gewife "fabric, fabric of fate" are related to the Indo - European root *uebh - "to weave, to weave" gewife. Herman Melville's poem "The Haglets", a precedent text for the American linguistic and cultural community the Haglets, reveals the theme of fate, which was so exciting for the outstanding writer of the XIX century, in the meanings of weaving and weaving. Seabirds, like a weaver's shuttle moving in a loom, weave a devastating fate for the ship:

Like shuttles hurrying in the looms
Aloft through rigging frayed they ply
Cross and recross – weave and inweave,
Then lock the web with clinching cry
Over the seas on seas that clasp
The weltering wreck where gurgling ends the
gasp (Melville. The Haglets).

Cutting, cutting, carving – another ancient meaning in the representation of fate. Norns sitting at the foot of the world tree carve the fate of people on tablets. The Indo-European root *skei "to cut" is derived from the Old Norse word skipta "to endow (fate)". The idea of carving, writing fate, was obviously close to Shakespeare. In particular, in Romeo and Juliet, after a duel with Paris, Romeo remarks that they are "on the same line in the book of disasters": One writ with me in sour misfortune"s book [Shakespeare. Romeo and Juliet). Later in Doctor Zhivago, the heroine of the novel Lara, responding to Yuri's request to tell about her husband, changes the book of disasters to the book of doom: "we are in the book of rock on the same line" (Pasternak. Doctor Zhivago). The same meaning is evident in the modern English phraseological unit handwriting on the wall "(bad) omen".

Doubts about the validity of including the term "concept" in scientific usage and recognizing the concept as an object of linguistic study have remained in the past and have given way to the search for an adequate description of it. At the present stage of development of linguistics, it has become obvious to most scientists that a concept is a speculative phenomenon, to which a certain form and content are attributed in a separate language group or several groups. The formal side of a concept is its name, which exists as a distinctive sign, and

therefore it is inscribed in the language system at the lexico-semantic level. The content of the concept is modeled and revealed in the speech activity of the language team. Precedent phenomena form a fragment of the semiotic model of the concept. Their content is telescopic, since the form of a precedent phenomenon correlates not with a particular linguistic meaning, but with meanings that are used for various manifestations of human life – everyday life, religious worship, political activity, pastime, and so on. The multi-layered content of precedent phenomena is the result of the interference of linguistic meanings, meanings, and interpretations. Studying them synchronously makes it possible to model the semiotic features of a particular concept that are characteristic of the cultural and linguistic community in a certain period of time. However, using only the synchronic approach is not enough, since it does not allow us to fully reveal the content of precedent phenomena and the fragment in the concept model that they form. The diachronic approach opens the way for the reconstruction of that part of the content of the precedent phenomenon, which, although present in it, is obscured by modern layers. The diachronic approach serves as a kind of filter, since it reveals the essential components of the concept that were formed in the past, inherited by the present and potentially significant for the future cultural and linguistic community.

As our research has shown, case statements and case situations reveal the content of the concept of FATE in a cognitive context. Consideration of precedent phenomena in the framework of a synchronous-diachronic approach allows us to expand the boundaries of the study of the interaction of language and world perception, the relationship of phenomena and events that take place in the real world, and their reflection in language and culture.

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